

EFFECTS OF DOMESTIC VIOLENCE ON CHILDREN'S COGNITIVE DEVELOPMENT IN RWANDA, A CASE OF GASABO DISTRICT

¹MARCELLA MUKASANO, ²Dr. MUGIRANEZA Faustin

^{1,2}(Mount Kenya University)

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Abstract: The research aimed to assess the effects of domestic violence on children's cognitive development in Gasabo District, Rwanda. Specifically, this study identified the types of domestic violence that influence children's cognitive development in Gasabo District, Rwanda, and determined the level of children's cognitive development that is due to the domestic violence. children's cognitive development in Gasabo District, Rwanda, analyzed the relationship between domestic violence and children's cognitive development in Gasabo District, Rwanda, and determined preventive measures of domestic violence types on children's cognitive development in Gasabo District, Rwanda. The sample size was 243, including 159 parents, 90 children's caregivers, and a child psychologist. Primary sources were gathered using questionnaires, interviews, and observation methods to triangulate the data. This study used purposive, stratified, and simple random sampling methods to derive a sample population from the respondents. The study applied both quantitative and qualitative methods complementarily in data collection and analysis. Content analysis helped qualitative data analysis, and quantitative data was presented using the statistical package for social sciences by descriptive statistics (frequency, percentage, mean, and standard deviation) and inferential statistics (correlational and regression analysis). For the first objective, results indicate that 79.2% strongly agreed that physical abuse indicates the types of domestic violence that have an impact on children's cognitive development. 82.6% strongly agreed that domestic violence affects children's cognitive development through emotional abuse and intimidation at home; 79.9% strongly agreed that Verbal Abuse: Coercion, Threats, and Blame demonstrates how domestic abuse can damage children's cognitive development; 77.2% strongly agreed that using male privilege indicates domestic abuse, which can have an influence on the cognitive development of children. 81.9% strongly agreed that domestic violence can include economic abuse, which can have an influence on cognitive development. The second objective found that parents strongly believe that poor communication skills, low reading rates, poor numeracy skills, pro-social behavior skills, and low school completion indicate a child's cognitive development. Children's caregivers also strongly agree that poor communication skills, low reading rates, low numeracy abilities, and low school completion indicate a lack of cognitive growth. Overall, these findings highlight the importance of understanding and addressing cognitive development in children. Results on the correlation between domestic violence and children's cognitive development in Gasabo District, Rwanda, indicated that most measures were positively associated with each other. Since the degree of significance was less than 0.05, in conclusion, the study shows that most commonly, physical abuse, sexual abuse, emotional abuse and intimidation, verbal abuse (coercion, threats, and blame), and using male privilege affect the cognitive development of children. The study found a strong positive association between poor communication skills, low literacy rates, and physical, sexual, emotional, verbal, and coercive abuse, as well as male privilege, and a strong correlation between pro-social behavior skills and abuse. The study concludes that domestic violence negatively impacts children's cognitive development in Rwanda. The study suggests that local leaders, police, school administrators, and affected children should collaborate to help children exposed to domestic violence. Schools should contact parents for therapy, notify local officials and police if necessary, and have a counselor to help children with psychological issues. The research suggests that the next study should be carried out on The Effects of Child Abuse and Exposure to Domestic Violence on Adolescent Internalizing and Externalizing Behavior Problems and Psychological Complications of the Children Exposed to Domestic Violence.

Keywords: Cognitive development, Domestic violence, Domestic violence, Medium of instruction, Skills Acquisition.

1. INTRODUCTION TO THE STUDY

Background of the Study

Domestic violence is a serious issue for people whose lives are touched by it, the social, health, and criminal justice institutions that respond to it, and society as a whole, which must face the consequences. While domestic violence is not a new occurrence, the last thirty years have witnessed an increase in public awareness and a rising political agreement that something has to be done, even if the specifics are unclear (McGreevy, 2019). Our knowledge of the presentation, dynamics, and consequences of domestic violence has evolved over time, necessitating the need to define what it is that society must address. This has not been an easy task, given that definitions and understandings of violence differ between research studies, locations, and cultural settings (European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights, 2014).

Globally, according to the 2016 UN World Report, domestic violence (DV) and violence against women and children are growing global problems. The poll indicates that at least 35% of women acknowledged experiencing domestic abuse (DV) from prior intimate relationships.

Domestic violence in Northern Ireland is described as threatening, dominating, coercive behavior, violence, or abuse (psychological, physical, verbal, sexual, financial, or emotional) perpetrated. Domestic violence is also referred to as domestic abuse or intimate partner violence in the literature. According to a British Crime Survey, half of individuals who experienced domestic abuse in the preceding year resided with a kid who was sixteen years old or younger (Tierolf, 2020). Within the United Kingdom, it is estimated that up to one million children have been exposed to domestic violence (UNICEF, 2018). Yet in spite of these stark statistics, there has been, until recently, a systemic failure by public agencies to appreciate that the presence of domestic violence should be an indicator of the importance of assessing the needs of children for both support and protection when living in the same household as the victim. This article seeks to summarize the key messages from the research literature on the prevalence and impact of domestic violence on children and to draw some conclusions about how professionals should respond to children's needs for safety and support. In India, various forms of direct and indirect violence against children are still normalized.

The Committee expressed concern over the lack of state-run shelters for women and children. CEDAW said that South Africa "cannot absolve itself of its obligation to provide protection and assistance to victims of domestic violence by delegating such services to NGO-run shelters without adequately funding them." The Committee concluded that South Africa failed to meet its obligation to investigate, prosecute, and punish cases of domestic violence, as well as to provide systematic and effective capacity building for the judiciary and law enforcement bodies, thereby violating South African women's right to live free from domestic violence.

The Committee has made 34 recommendations for action. These include effective law enforcement, policies ensuring adequate access to justice, protection, and victim support services, and measures dismantling patriarchal attitudes and discriminatory stereotypes that legitimize domestic violence.

Committee members visited South Africa in September 2019 to conduct a confidential inquiry into allegations by civil society organizations that women in South Africa were subjected to extreme levels of domestic violence. The Committee stressed that it had received the full cooperation of the Government of South Africa. In this regard, it remains ready to continue to work with the government, traditional and community leaders, and other stakeholders in the implementation of its recommendations, United National (2021).

Problem Statement

Many children who are exposed to domestic violence are also subjected to physical or mental abuse, are at a high risk of having long-term physical and mental health problems, and are more likely to utilize violence in their own relationships in the future. If you are a parent experiencing abuse, it may be difficult to know how to defend your child (Oash, 2021).

Domestic violence has serious consequences during a child's critical early years of development. Sadly, despite international law's prohibition on many forms of violence, severe punishment, neglect, and psychological abuse are all too widespread (UNODC, 2021). A significant number of children aged two to four years are subjected to harsh forms of discipline at home (UNICEF, 2017a; 2018). Infant survival is particularly vulnerable during their first year since they are fully dependent on adults (UNICEF, 2018). There is a high rate of co-occurrence of violence against women and violence against children (UNICEF, 2018). One in every four children under the age of five lives with a mother who has experienced intimate partner violence (UNICEF, 2017), and children who witness an episode of intimate partner violence are at risk of not reaching their

full developmental potential due to the risks of poverty, poor nutrition, a lack of access to basic services, early enrichment opportunities, and domestic violence (UNICEF, 2021).

Domestic and gender-based violence in Rwanda has gradually escalated over the last seven years. According to the Rwanda DHS 2019–2020, spouse violence (intimate partner violence) increased from 40% in 2015 to 46% in 2020, while the number of women and children who had suffered physical abuse from the age of 15 increased from 35% in 2014–15 to 37% in 2019–20. SHEMA, 2022, revealed psychological violence, physical violence, socioeconomic violence, and sexual violence as the most common forms of violence in Gasabo District.

Therefore, this study examined the Effects of domestic violence on children's cognitive development in Rwanda, specifically in Gasabo District.

Objectives of the Study

There are two categories of objective that this study is aimed to achieve which are general and specific objectives.

General Objective

This study assessed the effects of domestic violence on children's cognitive development in Gasabo District, Rwanda.

Specific Objectives

- (i) To identify the types of domestic violence that influence on children's cognitive development in Gasabo District, Rwanda.
- (ii) To determine the level of children's cognitive development that is due to the domestic violence children's cognitive development in Gasabo District, Rwanda.
- (iii) To analyze the relationship between domestic violence on children's cognitive development in Gasabo District, Rwanda
- (iv) To determine preventive measures of domestic violence types on children's cognitive development in Gasabo District, Rwanda.

Research Questions

The research questions were the following:

- (i) What are the types of domestic violence that influence on children's cognitive development in Gasabo District, Rwanda?
- (ii) To what the extend level of children's cognitive development that is due to the domestic violence children's cognitive development in Gasabo District, Rwanda.
- (iii) What is the relationship between domestic violence on children's cognitive development in Gasabo District, Rwanda?
- (iv) What are the preventive measures of domestic violence types on children's cognitive development in Gasabo District, Rwanda?

2. REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Theoretical Literature

Domestic violence that influence on children's cognitive development

According to Kart (2019), corporal punishment, slapping, and pinching are the most prevalent types of physical abuse suffered by victims. Physically abusive guardians rationalize their acts by emphasizing the need for teaching and discipline. They advocate for parental attention based on the "spare the rod, spoil the child" concept but end up physically abusing rather than correcting behaviors. The primary goal of discipline is to teach right from wrong rather than instill terror and other harsh emotional impacts through tyranny. Unpredictability is a common feature of physically abused children, particularly as adults. Unlike physical discipline, the kid is unaware of what is incorrect according to parental instruction, according to Bromfield (2010). Such victims are concerned about the potential of doing something wrong. They are concerned about engaging in behavior that may result in an offense. Second, abuse leads a youngster to be filled with rage. The severity of the abuse is determined by the parent's rage. Finally, the abuser emphasizes the necessity of instilling

behaviors via terror. Physical abuse is thus used as a kind of severe punishment to instill discipline. As a result of this awareness, the kid learns techniques to prevent parental maltreatment other than acquiring appropriate behaviors and maturing as a disciplined individual.

The level of children's cognitive development that is due to the domestic violence children's cognitive development

Intimate partner violence (IPV) is widely seen as a violation of human rights and a public health concern across the world (Campbell, 2002; Garcia-Moreno, Jansen, Ellsberg, Heise, & Watts, 2006; Tjaden & Thoennes, 2000). According to current statistics, violent crimes against intimate partners current or past husbands, boyfriends, and girlfriends are more common against women; these crimes encompass both fatal (homicide) and non-lethal (rape, assault) forms (Catalano, 2000). However, abusive behavior does not always involve tangible violence. Physical violence or abuse traditionally the most investigated and observable form must be distinguished from emotional, or psychological, abuse. Emotional abuse is defined as any nonphysical conduct or attitude that uses shame or terror to dominate, subdue, punish, or isolate another person (Engel, 2002). The current article focuses on this type of abuse while investigating its links to age and gender. Verbal abuse, dominance, control, isolation, mockery, or the exploitation of personal information for degrading purposes are all examples of emotional abuse (Follingstad, Coyne, & Gambone, 2005). It is typically a forerunner to physical abuse since it affects the victim's emotional and psychological well-being. Physical and mental abuse are highly correlated in batterer populations (Gondolf, Heckert, & Kimmel, 2002), and verbal abuse early in a relationship predicts eventual physical spousal violence (Schumacher & Leonard, 2005).

Gauvain and Richert (2016) define cognitive development as the process through which people acquire, organize, and learn to apply knowledge. The focus of cognitive development in psychology has frequently been limited to childhood. Cognitive growth, on the other hand, continues until adolescence and maturity. Language and information acquisition, reasoning, remembering, decision-making, problem solving, and exploration are all part of it (Von Eckardt, 1996). Much of the study on children's cognitive development focuses on thinking, developing knowledge, investigating, and problem solving (Carpendale & Lewis, 2015).

Empirical Literature

Through this study, different documents from various relevant authors carry out dissertation, books, journals, websites and reports written by others to the effect of domestic violence on children's cognitive development

Domestic violence that influence on children's cognitive development

The research conducted by Carlson (2020) suggests several implications for violence prevention and response programming and research. While VAC and IPV are affecting the majority of families and dyads, one-third of dyads are reporting both types of violence concurrently. Efforts to integrate prevention programming may consider addressing the associated factors, especially in families characterized by both IPV and VAC (i.e., women's education, socio-economic status, alcohol use, and emotional attachment between intimate partners). Furthermore, almost all factors associated with either the VAC 'only' or IPV 'only' dyads were also associated with the IPV and VAC dyads. More evaluative research is needed to better understand the potential 'spillover effects' of violence prevention interventions targeting either VAC or IPV on the prevention of other types of violence. For example, VAC prevention programs (especially ones that focus on poorer communities or programs that may focus on preventing violence against girls) should also measure their potential effects on preventing IPV. Likewise, IPV prevention programming that focuses on improving women's education or intimate partner relationships should also evaluate potential outcomes on VAC.

The prevalence of domestic violence

The study by Habumuremyi (2019) in Rwanda examined the prevalence of domestic violence there as well as men's participation in it, including its underlying causes, manifestations, effects, and mitigation measures. The following are important findings: According to 90% of respondents, males commit intimate partner violence (in all of its forms) mostly out of selfishness, which has an impact on the women, the children, the men who commit the violence, the home, the extended family, the neighborhood, and the nation. The women surveyed by the informant, 73.6% acknowledged having experienced domestic abuse in one or more forms. Intimate partner violence affects women from all socioeconomic backgrounds, including those with higher and lower levels of education, as well as those living in rural and metropolitan areas. While affected women informants make up 80% of the population in rural areas compared to 70% in urban areas, 62.9% of women informants with combined secondary and university degrees reported being impacted.

The most common types of intimate partner violence reported by women informants are: physical violence (beating), psychological violence (verbal abuse, coercion, threats, and blame), sexual violence (forced sexual relationships; denial of having sex), economic abuse (no control over household income), long-term deliberate silence at home, and sexual violence. The three main factors that have been linked to domestic violence are men's selfishness (mean 3.94), their need to dominate women (mean 3.93), their intoxication (mean 3.92), their excessive control over the household's finances, and their tendency to misappropriate the family's resources (mean 3.89).

The level of children's cognitive development that is due to the domestic violence children's cognitive development

In particular, its impacts on a child's development and greater vulnerability for subsequent mental health issues have been well-documented long-term effects of early adversity exposure (Kessler et al., 2010; Carr et al., 2013; Reuben et al., 2019).

The detrimental effects of exposure to intimate partner violence (IPV) are less thoroughly established in the literature than the effects of adversity such chronic neglect or abuse. The main causes of the lack of findings include incidences of IPV that frequently go unreported due to fear of repercussions or that are ameliorated by those affected. According to the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, intimate partner violence (IPV) is when one intimate partner uses coercive control over the other. This can include physical and sexual assault, threats of physical or sexual assault, and emotional abuse combined with physical and sexual assault (Saltzman et al., 1999; Breiding et al., 2015).

According to a Canadian incidence survey done by (Trocmé, 2018) found that the child exposure to IPV was identified in up to 34% of documented cases of child abuse and neglect Even though the alleged harm is deemed significant enough for the WHO to recommend standard IPV screening during pregnancy and to call for increased research on prevention of IPV's adverse effects, research on the effects of exposure to IPV during the perinatal phase and infancy is incredibly scarce. The majority of research has, as the official term implies, concentrated on the impacts of IPV on women. In addition, child exposure to IPV is sometimes addressed differently from child abuse. However, according to Carlson (2017), between 10% and 20% of US-born infants are exposed to IPV each year.

The research done by Zenana and Gleason (2019), ongoing caregiver connections that don't engender a sense of safety don't prevent the hormonal stress reactions from having a negative impact on an infant's brain development.

According to Cole et al. (2004), emotional regulation is the child's capacity to modify and respond to her degrees of arousal. It is crucial for the newborn to learn how to respond to emotions at this time because the frontal lobe, which is important for the development of emotion regulation, goes through a phase of fast growth and synaptic excess between the ages of 6 and 18 months (Dawson, 1994; Nelson and Bosquet, 2004). Because caregivers are a child's primary source of external control until self-regulation of emotion is fully formed, they are essential to the growth of emotion-regulating behaviors For a kid to learn and pay attention, which are critical abilities for academic success, emotional regulation skills are required (Perry, 2001; Cook et al., 2017). The child's ability to control arousal and stress is jeopardized by insensitive caregiving. According to Wittling and Schweiger (1993), Schore (2001), Cook et al. (2017), and others, a disturbed or highly aroused youngster does not feel safe and is unable to interact with people or things in the environment. As a result, less than ideal regulation on the part of the caregiver(s) might be harmful to the kid. In conclusion, the child's development, whether positive or negative, depends on these early experiences of sensitive regulation or insensitive mistreatment and dysregulation (Sroufe and Rutter, 1984; Tronick, 2018).

The relationship between domestic violence on children's cognitive development

According to the Australian study (Savopoulos, 2022) on intimate relationship violence and child and adolescent cognitive development, intimate partner violence (IPV) affects millions of children globally and is a problem for public health and human rights. This study sought to investigate the association between children's exposure to IPV and their cognitive development and to uncover related characteristics, such as features of parenting, whereas other papers focused on the emotional-behavioral functioning of children exposed to IPV. Key words related to IPV, such as domestic, family, partner, interparental, spousal, marital, violence, abuse, aggression, and assault, as well as key words related to cognitive functioning, such as neuropsychological, executive, intelligence, learning, and memory, were used to search the databases MEDLINE, PsycInfo, EMBASE, Family and Society Studies Worldwide, CINAHL, and ERIC. The review criteria, which included presenting an estimate of the association between IPV and cognition using direct evaluations of cognitive functioning, were satisfied by a total of 38 research. About 70% of research discovered a connection between IPV and worse cognitive functioning, with linguistic abilities and academic capabilities being the most often measured functional domains after general IQ. Fewer research evaluated children during middle childhood and adolescence; the majority of studies evaluated skills during early childhood. All cognitive domains and developmental stages showed similar results.

Numerous research has examined mediating and moderating processes in relation to the demographic, individual, and familial characteristics that are connected to IPV and cognition. The data imply that childhood exposure to IPV is linked to worse cognitive abilities throughout

Domestic violence

The research done in China by Haj-Yahia (2019) on the relationship between exposure to family violence in childhood and post-traumatic stress symptoms in young adulthood revealed that exposure to each pattern of family violence (i.e., witnessing interparental violence and experiencing parental violence) predicted higher levels of PTSS. Furthermore, social support was found to partially mediate the relationship between exposure to family violence during childhood and adolescence and current PTSS as well as its four symptoms, i.e., depression, sleep disturbance, dissociation, and anxiety.

The expression *exposure to family violence* consists of two patterns: (a) witnessing interparental violence and (b) direct experience with parental violence. In each of these patterns, both types of violence, i.e., physical violence (PV) and psychological aggression (PA), were examined. *Physical violence* is defined as "the intentional use of physical force with the potential for causing death, disability, injury, or harm. Physical violence includes but is not limited to scratching, pushing, shoving, throwing, grabbing, biting, choking, shaking, hair-pulling, slapping, punching, hitting, burning, use of a weapon (gun, knife, or another object), and use of restraints or one's body, size, or strength against another person" (Basile, 2015). Psychological aggression is defined as "the use of verbal and non-verbal communication with the intent to: a) harm another person mentally or emotionally, and/or b) exert control over another person" (Breiding, 2015).

According to a study on trauma-informed art and play therapy conducted in South Africa by Woollett (Woollett, 2020), children exhibit high rates of probable depressive and probable traumatic stress disorder (PTSD) symptoms (33% and 66%, respectively). By endline, there was a non-significant trend towards PTSD improvement (40.0–34.4, $p = 0.21$) and a substantial reduction in depressive symptoms (mean of 13.7–8.3, $p = 0.01$). Children said that by using their art to convey unpleasant feelings and memories of their moms, they were able to Some kids thought it would help manage difficult behaviors.

The effect of domestic violence on children

The study was done in Rwanda by Sezibera (2022) on the effect of a home-visiting parenting program to promote early childhood development and prevent violence. A cluster-randomized trial in Rwanda indicates that 284 geographic areas across three districts were used to recruit families with children between the ages of 6 and 36 months. Diffusion was avoided via cluster-level randomization (assigned 1:1 SM: UC). It was predicted that SM would enhance father involvement, decrease violence, and enhance child development. Anthropometric measurements of growth, the Malawi Development Assessment Tool (MDAT), and the Ages and Stages Questionnaire (ASQ-3) were used to evaluate developmental outcomes. Questions from the UNICEF Multiple Indicators Cluster Survey (MICS) and the Rwanda Demographic and Health Surveys (DHS) were used to measure violence. Using the Home Observation for Measurement of the Environment, father involvement was evaluated. Enumerators who were blinded performed interviews and developmental evaluations. In all, 541 SM families and 508 UC families were enlisted and included in the analyses, according to the results. Hot deck imputation was used to account for study attrition (2.0% children; 9.6% caregivers). As measured by the ASQ-3, children in SM households had greater gains in the areas of gross motor ($d = 0.162$, 95% CI 0.065 to 0.260), communication ($d = 0.081$, 95% CI 0.005 to 0.156), problem-solving ($d = 0.101$, 95% CI 0.002 to 0.179), and personal-social development ($d = 0.096$, 95% CI 0.015 to 0.177). Intimate partner violence was less common in SM households (incidence rate ratio, IRR = 0.616, 95% CI: 0.458 to 0.828), and there was a higher level of father involvement (OR = 1.592, 95% CI: 1.069 to 2.368). MDAT, or child growth, did not improve as a result of the intervention.

The research done in China by Haj-Yahia (2019) on the relationship between exposure to family violence in childhood and post-traumatic stress symptoms in young adulthood revealed that exposure to each pattern of family violence (i.e., witnessing interparental violence and experiencing parental violence) predicted higher levels of PTSS. Furthermore, social support was found to partially mediate the relationship between exposure to family violence during childhood and adolescence and current PTSS as well as its four symptoms, i.e., depression, sleep disturbance, dissociation, and anxiety.

Critical Review and Research Gap Identification

Huth-Bock (2015) conducted a study on the direct and indirect consequences of domestic violence on the cognitive functioning of preschoolers. The study reveals that after adjusting for SES and child maltreatment, children who had witnessed domestic violence had considerably worse verbal ability than no witnesses, but there were no group differences

in visual-spatial abilities. Domestic violence also had an indirect impact on both types of intellectual ability due to its effects on mother depression and the intellectual quality of the home environment. The study's strengths and weaknesses, as well as the ramifications, are examined; however, this study failed to indicate the relationship between domestic violence and children's cognitive development.

The study by Laurenzi (2021) on associations between young children's exposure to household violence and behavioral problems: evidence from a rural Kenyan sample suggests that child exposure to violence in various forms is widespread and is related to worse outcomes in early children. Community-based parenting and early childhood development programs are well-positioned to address home violence in LMIC settings, but they must be supported to create a deeper awareness of violence and its immediate and long-term implications.

Theoretical Framework

The theoretical framework is the structure that can hold or support a theory of a research study. The theoretical framework introduces and describes the theory that explains why the research problem under study exists.

Social control theory

According to social control theory, the formation of a social tie is a psychological condition that acts as a buffer against risk variables in life (Hirschi, 1969). Attachment to a good institution, dedication to conventional paths of accomplishment, and trust in the validity of societal order, according to Hirschi (1969), are crucial aspects in building a social tie. Deviant conduct is effectively controlled by an established social link (Catalano, Haggerty, Oesterle, Fleming, & Hawkins, 2004). However, inadequate social relationships may raise the chance of delinquency or criminality. Researchers interested in social control theory frequently explore school bonding and school connection, which overlap with the emotional components of school participation. School bonding was characterized by Hawkins and Weis (1985) as an attachment to prosocial peers, dedication to academic and social activities at school, and belief in the established norms for school conduct (Simons-Morton, Crump, Haynie, & Saylor, 1999). Resnick et al. (1997) investigated how school connection might protect adolescents from harm. School connection, as a possible protective factor for adolescents, may buffer against delinquency and deviant conduct, operate as a preventative force for school dropouts, and give protection from harmful influences. The social development model has been refined and evolved from social control theory (e.g., Catalano & Hawkins, 1996; Hawkins, 1997; Hawkins & Lishner, 1987).

Conceptual Framework

Mwiseneza, (2015) defines conceptual framework as an image of the phenomena to be investigated. The diagram below will show the relationship indicators of independent and dependent variable with intervening variables.

Fig 1

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research design

According to McCombes (2019), a research design, also known as a research strategy, is a method for addressing a set of questions. It is a framework that includes methods and procedures for data gathering, analysis, and interpretation. Descriptive research is defined as a purposeful process of gathering, analyzing, classifying, and tabulating data about current conditions, practices, processes, trends, and cause-and-effect relationships, and then making adequate and accurate interpretations about such data with or without, or sometimes with minimal, statistical methods. Furthermore, this technique determines the current state of facts in a group under investigation and provides either qualitative or quantitative, or both, descriptions of the group's overall features as findings (Roberston, 2018). This study employed a descriptive survey research design and included both quantitative and qualitative approaches. On the one hand, a survey was used with the quantitative technique, in which questionnaires will be sent to respondents over the course of the study.

Target population

A research population is the group of individuals that the intervention intends to conduct research on and draw conclusions from (Barnsbee, 2018). The population in this study consisted of one hundred fifty parents including female and male, ninety children's caregivers, and three children's mental psychologists, totaling 243 respondents from three sectors in Gasabo district, such as Kimironko, Gisozi, and Kinyinya.

Table 3.1: targeted population and simple size

Sectors	PARENTS	CHILDREN CAREGIVERS	Child Psychologist
Kimironko	50	30	1
Gisozi	50	30	1
Kinyinya	50	30	1
Total	150	90	3

Source: primary data 2023

Sample design

The technique used to select the sample population is called sampling design, and it enables the researcher to generalize the findings to the complete group targeted in the study (Cochran, 2016).

Sample size determination

According to (2021, Kibuacha) "The number of people that comprise a research study to represent a population is referred to as sample size." The word "sample size" refers to the total number of respondents in the survey, which is generally broken down by demographics such as age, gender, and region to ensure that the total sample reflects the whole population.

participants. This means that the total sample population was composed of 243 respondents, composed of 150 parents, 90 children's caregivers, and 3 child psychologists.

Sampling Technique

Purposive sampling, according to Nikolopoulou (2022), refers to a class of non-probability sampling procedures in which units are chosen based on features that you require in your sample. To put it another way, unit populations are chosen "on purpose" in purposive sampling. A simple random sample is a randomly selected subset of a population. In this sampling method, each member of the population has an exactly equal chance of being selected (Thomas, 2020). This study used purposive sampling techniques to choose a child psychologist and also used simple random sampling to choose the parents and children. These techniques were used by the researcher based on the experience, qualities, and knowledge of all respondents to provide valuable information.

Data Collection Methods

Data collection is a systematic procedure for compiling measurements or observations. Data gathering enables you to get first-hand information and unique insights into your study challenge, whether you are conducting research for corporate,

governmental, or academic objectives. This study employed data-gathering methods, including questionnaires and documentation. Research procedures that were used in data analysis are discussed.

Data Collection Instruments

According to Satya (2022), a questionnaire is a research tool made up of a list of questions (items) designed to record respondents' replies in a consistent way. In this study, the questionnaire included a series of open questions that helped the researcher get the needed information from the respondents, and the questionnaire was distributed to the respondents to collect qualitative data considering the set objectives of the study. 1 strongly disagrees, 2 strongly disagrees, 3 is neutral, 4 agrees, and 5 strongly agree. The respondents will be a teacher and a principal.

Questions were divided into four groups: A, B, C, and D. Section A contained demographic data such as gender, age, academic qualifications, and years of experience of parents and children. Section B was completed with questions from parents and children regarding how domestic violence affects children's cognitive development.

Administration for Data Collection Instrument

Before beginning data collection, the researcher was introduced to the district education officer, head teachers, and other stakeholders in the field through a referral letter from Mount Kenya University. After being given permission, the researcher sits in a private room with groups of six to ten participants, with a focus on domestic violence and cognitive development. It took one month to collect data from all respondents and participants.

4. FINDINGS, INTERPRETATION AND DISCUSSION

The types of domestic violence that influence on children's cognitive development in Gasabo District, Rwanda

The research identified the identify the types of domestic violence that influence on children's cognitive development in Gasabo District, Rwanda. The following statement were proposed such as Physical abuse as indicates the types of domestic violence has an impact on children's cognitive development, Domestic violence affects children's cognitive development through emotional abuse and intimidation at home, Verbal Abuse: Coercion, Threats, and Blame demonstrates how domestic abuse can damage children's cognitive development, Using Male Privilege indicates domestic abuse, which can have an influence on the cognitive development of children and Domestic violence can include economic abuse, which can have an influence on cognitive development. The following tables show how the participants Respond to the following statements.

Table 4.5 parents perception on the types of domestic violence that influence on children's cognitive development in Gasabo District, Rwanda

Statements	Strongly Disagree		Disagree		Neutral		Agree		Strongly Agree		Mean	Std
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%		
Physical abuse indicates the types of domestic violence has an impact on children's cognitive development.	9	6.0	7	4.7	8	5.4	7	4.7	118	79.2	1.536	1.171
Domestic violence affects children's cognitive development through emotional abuse and intimidation at home.	2	1.3	7	4.7	8	5.4	9	6.0	123	82.6	1.503	1.171
Verbal Abuse: Coercion, Threats, and Blame demonstrates how domestic abuse can damage children's cognitive development.	5	3.4	7	4.7	9	6.0	9	6.0	119	79.9	1.537	1.17
Using Male Privilege indicates domestic abuse, which can have an influence on the cognitive development of children.	8	5.4	8	5.4	12	8.1	6	4.0	115	77.2	1.537	1.17
Domestic violence can include economic abuse, which can have an influence on cognitive development.	0	0.0	7	4.7	10	6.7	10	6.7	122	81.9	1.543	1.21

Source: Primary Data (2023)

Results in Table 4.5 evidenced the perception of parent's on the types of domestic violence that influence on children's cognitive development in Gasabo District, Rwanda. Accordingly 118 (79.2%) parent strongly agreed that Physical abuse indicates the types of domestic violence has an impact on children's cognitive development, 123(82.6%) parent strongly agreed that Domestic violence affects children's cognitive development through emotional abuse and intimidation at home, 119(79.9%) parent strongly agreed that Verbal Abuse: Coercion, Threats, and Blame demonstrates how domestic abuse can damage children's cognitive development, 115(77.2%) parent strongly agreed that Using Male Privilege indicates domestic abuse, which can have an influence on the cognitive development of children, 122(81.9%) parent strongly agreed that Domestic violence can include economic abuse, which can have an influence on cognitive development. As shown the high number of respondents strongly agreed that the above statement indicate the types domestic violence in Gasabo District

The level of children's cognitive development that is due to the domestic violence children's cognitive development in Gasabo District, Rwanda

This study determined the level of children's cognitive development that is due to the domestic violence children's cognitive development in Gasabo District, Rwanda.

The relationship between domestic violence on children's cognitive development in Gasabo District, Rwanda

Correlation between domestic violence and children's cognitive development in Gasabo District, Rwanda

		Physical Abuse	sexual Abuse	Emotional Abuse Intimidation	Verbal Abuse: Coercion, Threats, Blame	Using Male Privilege	Poor communication skills	Low literacy rates among children	Poor child numeracy skills	Pro-social Behaviour Skills
Physical Abuse	Pearson Correlation	1								
	Sig. (2-tailed)									
	N	240								
sexual Abuse	Pearson Correlation	.387**	1							
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000								
	N	240	240							
Emotional Abuse Intimidation	Pearson Correlation	.180**	.426**	1						
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.005	.000							
	N	240	240	240						
Verbal Abuse: Coercion, Threats, Blame	Pearson Correlation	.212**	.363**	.296**	1					
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.001	.000	.000						
	N	240	240	240	240					
Using Male Privilege	Pearson Correlation	.069	.046	.066	.059	1				
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.287	.482	.307	.362					
	N	240	240	240	240	240				
Poor communication skills	Pearson Correlation	.781**	.251**	.133*	.134*	.027	1			
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.023	.038	.672				
	N	240	240	240	240	240	240			
Low literacy rates among children	Pearson Correlation	.805**	.270**	.145*	.165*	.887**	.030	1		
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.025	.011	.000	.638			
	N	240	240	240	240	240	240	240		
Poor child numeracy skills	Pearson Correlation	.855**	.276**	.122	.136*	.031	.865**	.885**	1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.059	.036	.637	.000	.000		
	N	240	240	240	240	240	240	240	240	
Pro-social Behaviour Skills	Pearson Correlation	.693**	.309**	.073	.708**	.675**	.760**	.748**	.695**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.023	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	
	N	240	240	240	240	240	240	240	240	240

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Source: Primary Data (2023)

Findings from Table 4.9 indicated A strong relationship was established Poor communication skills and the following statements as follows, with Physical Abuse ($r=.781^{**}$, $p\text{-value}=0.000$), sexual Abuse ($.270^{**}$ $p\text{-value}=0.000$), with Emotional Abuse & Intimidation ($.133^{*}$, $p\text{-value}=0.023$) Verbal Abuse: ($r=.134^{*}$, $p\text{-value}=.038$) Coercion, Threats, & Blame, Using Male Privilege ($r=.496^{**}$, $p\text{-value}=0.000$). The association is positively related because the $p\text{-value}$ was less than 0.05, explaining that Poor communication skills affect Physical Abuse, sexual Abuse, Emotional Abuse & Intimidation, Verbal Abuse: Coercion, Threats, & Blame and Using Male Privilege and vice versa.

For Low literacy rates among children A strong relationship was established with Physical Abuse at ($r=.805^{**}$, $p\text{-value}=0.000$), sexual Abuse ($.251^{**}$ $p\text{-value}=0.000$), with Emotional Abuse & Intimidation ($.145^{*}$, $p\text{-value}=0.025$) Verbal Abuse: ($r=.165^{*}$ $p\text{-value}=0.000$). Coercion, Threats, & Blame, Using Male Privilege ($r=.675^{**}$ $p\text{-value}=0.000$). The association is positively related because the $p\text{-value}$ was less than 0.05, explaining that Poor communication skills affect Physical Abuse, sexual Abuse, Emotional Abuse & Intimidation, Verbal Abuse: Coercion, Threats, & Blame and Using Male Privilege and vice versa. For Pro-social Behaviour Skills A strong relationship was established with Physical Abuse at ($r=.693^{**}$, $p\text{-value}=0.000$), sexual Abuse ($.309^{**}$ $p\text{-value}=0.000$), with Emotional Abuse & Intimidation ($.073^{*}$, $p\text{-value}=0.025$) Verbal Abuse: ($r=.708^{**}$ $p\text{-value}=0.023$). Coercion, Threats, & Blame, Using Male Privilege ($r=.887^{**}$ $p\text{-value}=0.000$). The association is positively related because the $p\text{-value}$ was less than 0.05, explaining that Poor communication skills affect Physical Abuse, sexual Abuse, Emotional Abuse & Intimidation, Verbal Abuse: Coercion, Threats, & Blame and Using Male Privilege and vice versa. (alexandre, 2020) examined the link between malnutrition and poor cognitive performance in public elementary school students aged 7-14. It used Raven's Progressive Matrices Test, Revised Conflict Tactics Scales, and BMI to evaluate cognitive development. Results showed that 63.3% of individuals had below-average intellectual development, with malnutrition found in 9.5% of the population. The study also found that exposure to domestic violence negatively influenced cognitive function, suggesting that the issue of malnutrition must be addressed.

Regression Coefficients between independent variable and poor communication skills

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
		B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.
1	(Constant)	1.179	.106		11.080	.000
	Physical Abuse	-.100	.072	-.118	-1.381	.010
	sexual Abuse	-.006	.080	-.307	-.069	.006
	Emotional Abuse & Intimidation	&-.197	.074	-.233	-2.653	.009
	Verbal Abuse: Coercion, Threats, & Blame	.101	.067	.433	1.499	.001
	Using Male Privilege	.353	.058	.412	6.076	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Poor communication skills

Source: Primary data (2023)

Findings in Table 4.10 from respondents shows the regression analysis between dependent variable as poor communication skills, x: independent variable as physical abuse, sexual abuse, emotional abuse and intimidation, verbal abuse: coercion, threats, and blame, and using male privilege, according to the result from respondents, physical abuse was negatively statistically significant with poor communication skills ($B = -.118$, $p\text{-value} = .0010$), sexual abuse was statistically significant with poor communication skills ($B = -.307$, $p\text{-value} = .006$), emotional abuse and intimidation were significantly affecting poor communication skills ($B = -.233$, $p\text{-value} = .009$), using male privilege was positively statistically significant with poor communication skills ($B = .433$, $p\text{-value} = .000$), and verbal abuse: coercion, threats, and blame value are significant affecting poor communication skills ($B = .412$, $p\text{-value} = .000$). The result of the regression analysis indicated that there is a significant relationship between independent variables and poor communication skills. According to (Wyatt, 2017), nurses confront challenges in adopting domestic violence screening because of a lack of information and training. The interviews yielded six themes: Preparedness, Discomfort, Taboo, Disenchantment, Presumption, and Evolving Realizations. The study reveals that the work environment and colleagues impact the amount of care with which nurses screen for domestic abuse, emphasizing the process's distinctive interpersonal aspect.

Regression Coefficients between independent variable and Low literacy rates among children.

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta			
1	(Constant)	1.306	.123			10.647	.000
	Physical Abuse	-.079	.084	-.687		-.946	.005
	sexual Abuse	-.018	.093	-.720		-.195	.034
	Emotional Abuse & Intimidation	-.112	.085	-.324		-1.310	.021
	Verbal Abuse: Coercion, Threats, & Blame	.099	.077	.122		1.276	.003
	Using Male Privilege	.211	.067	.230		3.157	.002

a. Dependent Variable: Low literacy rates among children

Source: Primary data (2023)

Findings in Table 4.11 from respondents of this study show the regression analysis between the dependent variable as low literacy rates among children, x: independent variable as physical abuse, sexual abuse, emotional abuse, and intimidation, verbal abuse: coercion, threats, and blame, and using male privilege. The above shows that physical abuse was negatively statistically significant with low literacy rates among children ($B = -.687$, $p\text{-value} = .005$), sexual abuse was statistically significant with low literacy rates among children ($B = -.720$, $p\text{-value} = .034$), emotional abuse and intimidation were significantly affecting low literacy rates among children ($B = -.324$, $p\text{-value} = .021$), using male privilege was positively statistically significant with low literacy rates among children ($B = .122$, $p\text{-value} = .003$), and verbal abuse: coercion, threats, and blame value were significant affecting low literacy rates among children ($B = .230$, $p\text{-value} = .002$). The result of the regression analysis indicated that there is a significant relationship between independent variables and low literacy rates among children. (Mueller, 2017) investigate the effects of newborn exposure to intimate partner violence (IPV) on socio-emotional and neurological development. Although most studies focus on mothers or older children, the developmental impacts of early childhood exposure are less extensively studied. Exposure wreaks havoc on emotional and cognitive development, the Hypothalamus-Pituitary-Adrenal axis, and brain areas associated with witnessing. The scarcity of research on IPV during infancy and its impact on caregiving and baby development emphasizes the importance of preventative efforts.

Regression analysis between Independent Variable and Poor child numeracy skills

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta			
1	(Constant)	1.089	.120			9.081	.000
	Physical Abuse	.013	.082	.014		.163	.007
	sexual Abuse	.152	.091	.163		1.677	.015
	Emotional Abuse & Intimidation	-.195	.084	-.205		-2.336	.020
	Verbal Abuse: Coercion, Threats, & Blame	-.196	.076	-.230		-2.590	.010
	Using Male Privilege	.461	.065	.478		7.043	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Poor child numeracy skills

Source: Primary data (2023)

Findings in Table 4.12 from respondents to this study show the regression analysis between the dependent variable as poor child numeracy skills among children and the independent variable as physical abuse, sexual abuse, emotional abuse, and intimidation; verbal abuse: coercion, threats, and blame; and using male privilege. The above shows that physical abuse was positively statistically significant with poor child numeracy skills ($B = .014$, $p\text{-value} = .007$), sexual abuse was positively statistically significant with low literacy rates among children ($B = .163$, $p\text{-value} = .015$), emotional abuse and intimidation were negatively significant affecting poor child numeracy skills ($B = -.205$, $p\text{-value} = .020$), using male privilege was negatively statistically significant with low literacy rates among children ($B = -.230$, $p\text{-value} = .010$), and verbal abuse: coercion, threats, and blame value were positive significant affecting poor child numeracy skills ($B = .478$, $p\text{-value} = .000$). The result of the regression analysis indicated that there is a significant relationship between independent variables and

Poor child numeracy skills. (Spangaro, 2019) reported the systematic review of interventions to minimize sexual and intimate partner violence in war, post-conflict, and humanitarian crises: personnel, community mobilization, social norms, economic empowerment, empowerment, and survivor responses. Interventions in economic empowerment and gendered social norms were the most prevalent. Four studies found a non-significant trend in the prevalence of sexual/intimate relationship violence. Some economic empowerment, social standards, and survivor treatments have been shown to enhance mental health outcomes. Future study should look at the most successful ways to offer social norms interventions, as well as collaborate with local partners.

Regression analysis between Independent Variable and Pro-social Behaviour Skills

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
		B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.
1	(Constant)	1.391	.139		10.026	.000
	Physical Abuse	-.113	.094	-.211	-1.201	.031
	sexual Abuse	.302	.105	.300	2.881	.004
	Emotional Abuse & Intimidation	-.134	.097	-.341	-1.385	.000
	Verbal Abuse: Coercion, Threats, & Blame	-.172	.087	-.187	-1.970	.050
	Using Male Privilege	.202	.076	.195	2.673	.008

a. Dependent Variable: Pro-social Behaviour Skills

Source: Primary data (2023)

Findings in Table 4.13 from respondents to this study show the regression analysis between the dependent variable as pro-social behavior skills and the independent variable as physical abuse, sexual abuse, emotional abuse, and intimidation; verbal abuse: coercion, threats, and blame; and using male privilege. The above shows that physical abuse was positively statistically significant with pro-social behavior skills (B = -.211, p-value = .031), sexual abuse was positively statistically significant with pro-social behavior skills (B = .300, p-value = .004), emotional abuse and intimidation were negatively significant affecting pro-social behavior skills (B = -.341, p-value = .000), using male privilege was negatively statistically significant with low literacy rates among children (B = -.187, p-value = .050), and verbal abuse: coercion, threats, and blame value were positive significant affecting pro-social behavior skills (B = .195, p-value = .007). The result of the regression analysis indicated that there is a significant relationship between independent variables and pro-social behavior skills. Piotrowski (2022) explores prosocial behavior in siblings exposed to intimate partner violence (IPV) and its relationship with factors such as violence exposure, sibling spacing, child age, self-esteem, and relationship quality. Results showed that prosocial behavior was positively associated with warmth and sibling spacing but not with IPV or child self-esteem. Declined prosocial behaviors were positively associated with physical IPV and negatively with child age. The study sheds light on resilience in children exposed to IPV.

5. SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Summary of Findings

This chapter discussed the findings from the four objectives, such as identifying the types of domestic violence that influence children's cognitive development in Gasabo District, Rwanda; determining the level of children's cognitive development that is due to domestic violence; analyzing the relationship between domestic violence and children's cognitive development in Gasabo District, Rwanda; and determining preventive measures for the types of domestic violence that influence children's cognitive development in Gasabo District, Rwanda.

The types of domestic violence that influence children's cognitive development in Gasabo District, Rwanda

The result indicated that 83.3% strongly agreed that physical abuse, as well as domestic violence, can have an impact on my cognitive development. 88.9% strongly agreed that domestic emotional abuse and intimidation can have an impact on cognitive development. 78.4% strongly agreed that Domestic Violence: Coercion, Threats, and Blame shows how domestic violence can harm my cognitive development. 80.0% strongly agreed that male privilege as a sort of domestic abuse has an impact on my cognitive development, and 87.8% strongly agreed that economic abuse has had an impact on my cognitive growth. From the response of the parents, it is clear that physical abuse, sexual abuse, emotional abuse and

intimidation, verbal abuse (coercion, threats, and blame), and using male privilege are all examples of domestic violence in Gasabo district. This proved that physical abuse, sexual abuse, emotional abuse and intimidation, verbal abuse (coercion, threats, and blame), and using male privilege are the types of domestic violence that affect the cognitive development of children in Gasabo district, Rwanda.

The level of children's cognitive development that is due to domestic violence children's cognitive development in Gasabo District, Rwanda

This research analyzed the level of children's cognitive development that is due to domestic violence. children's cognitive development in Gasabo District, Rwanda

Results discussed in Chapter 4 Results in the perception of parents 79.4% of parents strongly agreed that poor communication skills might indicate a child's cognitive development level; 82.6% of parents agreed It is strongly agreed that children's low reading rates are markers of their cognitive development. Additionally, 77.9% of parents Strongly agreed that poor kid numeracy skills indicate a child's cognitive development level, 68.5%. parents Strongly agreeing that pro-social behavior skills are indications of a child's cognitive development, 78.5% of parents Strongly agreed that low levels of school completion indicate poor cognitive development in youngsters.

Results in the perception of children's caregivers showed that 80.0% of children's caregivers strongly agreed that their cognitive development level may be shown by their poor communication abilities, and 78.9% of children's caregivers strongly agreed that low reading rates in children are indicators of their cognitive development. Additionally, 75.6% of children's caregivers strongly agreed that their low numeracy abilities suggest a lack of cognitive growth, and 66.6% of children's caregivers strongly agreed that their cognitive progress is reflected in their pro-social behavior skills.

The relationship between domestic violence and children's cognitive development in Gasabo District, Rwanda

The correlation and regression results established The study found a strong relationship between poor communication skills and physical, sexual, emotional, verbal, and coercive abuse, as well as male privilege. The association was positive, with a p-value of less than 0.05. Low literacy rates among children also showed a strong relationship with physical, sexual, emotional, verbal, and coercive abuse. Pro-social behavior skills also showed a strong relationship with physical, sexual, emotional, and verbal abuse, with a p-value of less than 0.05.

The preventive measures of domestic violence types on children's cognitive development in Gasabo District, Rwanda

The study reveals that education, leadership, and legislative measures are effective in preventing domestic violence, while 82.7% recommend seeking guidance from specialists for health, legal,

Conclusions

Reconsidering findings from this present research, it concludes: To the first research objectives, the study reveals that the study found that physical and emotional abuse, as well as domestic violence, can negatively impact cognitive development. Male privilege and economic abuse also contribute to cognitive growth. Caregivers also noted that children's cognitive development can be influenced by poor communication, low reading rates, low numeracy abilities, and pro-social behavior skills. Overall, these factors contribute to cognitive development.

The researcher reveals that the study found that poor communication skills, low reading rates, poor numeracy skills, pro-social behavior skills, and low school completion indicate a child's cognitive development. Children's caregivers also strongly agree that poor communication skills, low reading rates, low numeracy abilities, and low school completion indicate a lack of cognitive growth. Overall, these findings highlight the importance of understanding and addressing cognitive development in children.

Results from objective three reveal that there was a relationship between domestic violence and children's cognitive development in Gasabo District and that they were positively and statistically correlated since most of their levels of significance were greater than 0.05 in association with children's cognitive development in Gasabo District.

The result for the fourth objectives indicate education, leadership, and legislative measures are successful in avoiding domestic violence, and 82.7% urge obtaining health, legal, psychiatric, or other counsel from professionals.

Recommendations to the Study

Based on the research findings it was recommended that the government must continue to strengthen its controls in order to successfully restrict the crime. It was also determined that certain pupils in Rwandan elementary schools do not study successfully, and that domestic violence is one of the contributing causes. This also means that considerable steps are required to remedy the problem. The study's findings will help the authorities understand the many types of domestic abuse. Based on its results, the research advised that elementary school administrators in Rwanda attempt to identify and closely analyze pupils who exhibit aberrant behavior. When it is discovered that these students have been subjected to domestic violence, the school's administration should put in place special mechanisms to address the issue, such as contacting the parents for counseling, reporting the perpetrator parents to police or local authorities, and assisting the affected students in a special way, such as providing extra care in their studies.

To assist children who have been exposed to domestic violence, local leaders, police, school administrators, and the affected children should work together. When they are recognized, the school should contact the parents right once to arrange for therapy. If this does not work, the school should promptly notify local officials as well as the police to follow up on the situation and resolve it. Finally, to give further assistance to students afflicted by domestic abuse,

Every school in Rwanda shall have a counselor whose primary responsibility is to assist kids suffering from psychological issues, particularly those who have been victims of domestic abuse. The counselor should be capable of dealing with domestic violence situations. Domestic violence has a negative impact on children's education, according to the conclusions of this study, and greater efforts should be taken to eliminate this risk in Rwandan households.

Suggestions for Further Studies

The study recommends future researches to carry out studies in the following subject: The Effects of Child Abuse and Exposure to Domestic Violence on Adolescent Internalizing and Externalizing Behavior Problems and Psychological complications of the children exposed to domestic violence

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